

Printable ADA-GEL-based composite inks containing Zn-doped bioactive inorganic fillers for skeletal muscle biofabrication[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Bioprinting shows significant promise in advancing medical treatments by offering patient-specific solutions for repairing skeletal muscle tissues. Zinc (Zn) is one of the key ions in the human body involved in the development of myogenic cells. This study investigates the integration of Zn-doped bioactive inorganic fillers (BIFs) into alginate-dialdehyde-gelatin (ADA-GEL) as composite ink for bioprinting applications. BIFs were mesoporous calcium-silicate-based bioactive glass nanoparticles with nominal composition: 80% SiO₂-X% CaO-Y% ZnO (X = 20, 18, 15, or 10; Y = 0, 2, 5, or 10; mol%). Ion release profiles confirmed that the addition of Zn ions prevented the burst release of Si and Ca ions. The incorporation of BIFs, particularly at higher dopant concentrations, significantly affected the hydrogel swelling and mechanical properties. With increasing concentration of Zn ions (to 5 mol%), the hydrogels exhibited greater dimensional swelling after 24 h of incubation in aqueous solutions, while all compositions lost weight over time after the initial swelling phase. Indirect cell studies demonstrated that 0.1 wt% BIFs extracts, obtained after 24 h-incubation in a cell culture medium, were cytocompatible with C2C12 cells. Furthermore, bioprinted C2C12 cells encapsulated in the bioinks showed a clear increase in cell number after seven days of culture. In particular, cells in the composite inks containing Zn-BIFs exhibited higher spreading, elongation, and alignment than those in pure ADA-GEL, indicating the biological activity provided by the Zn-BIF particles. This study introduces therefore an effective formulation of ADA-GEL-based composite bioinks enriched with Zn-containing nanoparticles for skeletal muscle tissue engineering applications.

1. Introduction

The cornerstone of a successful tissue engineering application lies in the scaffold, which not only provides support to surrounding healthy tissues but also, when combined with cells, favors cell development and delivery of growth factors at the damaged sites [1,2]. Skeletal muscle regeneration could also profit from the development of tissue engineering therapies as the natural healing and self-regeneration capabilities of skeletal muscle are limited to minor and small-scale defects [3–5]. Severe muscular diseases and injuries, which are complicated to treat and often lead to tissue dysfunction, pose challenges to the repair process [6,7]. As a potential treatment, transplanted scaffolds composed

of biomaterials, cells, and biomolecules at the site of injury present a promising strategy to support the regeneration of healthy tissues [2,8]. Bioprinting is an additive manufacturing method to fabricate three-dimensional (3D) cell-laden constructs, enabling the layer-by-layer deposition of materials together with cells and extracellular matrix (ECM) elements in one-step [9,10]. The integration of cells within the inks enables the creation of a 3D environment surrounding cells, more accurately replicating the natural conditions found in the human body [9,11,12].

Hydrogels are popularly used as inks in bioprinting because of their structural mimicry of the ECM, tunable properties for 3D printing, and most importantly the suitable microenvironment to shield cells from

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excessive shear stress during the 3D printing process [13,14]. In most cases, hydrogels consist of hydrophilic polymer networks that are able to absorb and retain large amounts of water and swell up to an impressive extent of their initial sizes [15–17]. Their capability of water retention as well as their flexibility and porosity are crucial for cells being encapsulated in the inks. Alginate-dialdehyde-gelatin (ADA-GEL) as hydrogel is conveniently used in bioprinting as it comprises two naturally derived polymers forming an interpenetrating network exhibiting biocompatibility, non-toxic and non-immunogenic behavior [18,19]. The tunable degradability, mechanical, and rheological properties are also benefits held by ADA-GEL hydrogels [18,19]. By varying the oxidation degree of ADA, employing different types and concentrations of divalent ions as crosslinkers for ADA (e.g. CaCl_2 , BaCl_2), and adjusting the process temperature to account for the thermally responsive GEL, ADA-GEL based inks can exhibit a broad spectrum of properties fitted for both hard and soft tissue engineering applications [20–23]. Even though hydrogels exhibit great properties in terms of printability and tunability, the system frequently encounters limitations in mechanical strength and lacks essential signaling elements to promote cell development [24,25]. Furthermore, using hydrogel alone makes it difficult to achieve promising mimicry of the complex architecture of native tissues [26]. To address the challenges, the concept of the formation of hybrid and composite hydrogels caught researchers' attention, allowing them to integrate the advantages of multimaterial systems and remedy the drawbacks of single component hydrogels. For instance, the combination of hydrogels with electrospun fibers [27–30], inorganic fillers such as bioactive glasses and calcium phosphates [31–34], and magnetic or electric conductive particles, e.g. carbon nanotubes, polypyrrole nanoparticles, and metals [35–38], are being increasingly investigated for various tissue engineering approaches targeting different cell types.

Bioactive glasses (BGs) were first introduced in 1969 [39] and have a long history of being successfully applied to stimulate bone tissue regeneration due to their intrinsic bioactivity [40,41]. In recent years, more benefits of BGs have been introduced in soft tissue engineering, mostly as bioactive inorganic fillers (BIFs) in biopolymers or hydrogels, acting as carriers for therapeutic ions [32]. With tailored synthesis methods and precursor elements, ions can be introduced to the BG network to be later released into the environment when BG particles degrade, aiming at supporting wound closure and regeneration of target tissues. It was reported that calcium-silicate-based particles composed of 80% SiO_2 exhibited enhanced support for myoblast proliferation and differentiation compared to those composed of 100% SiO_2 or 60% SiO_2 [42]. An important group of BIFs for incorporation in biopolymers and hydrogels is represented by mesoporous BG nanoparticles (MBGNs) obtained by sol-gel approaches [43]. In our study, MBGNs comprising 80% SiO_2 were selected, which were synthesized using an established synthesis method, and distinct dopant ions, resulting in nanoparticles with differing characteristics and compositions. Zinc (Zn) is a trace element in the human body, which is mainly found in bone, liver, kidneys, and muscles [44]. It plays an essential role in the repairing process and wound healing in these tissues [44,45]. Zinc ions act as cofactors in maintaining various physiological functions, including enzyme synthesis and function, cellular regulation, and metabolism [46,47]. While there is ongoing debate regarding the optimal effective concentration of Zn ions for medical applications, several studies have demonstrated the positive effects of Zn ions on myoblast development and in the process of skeletal muscle regeneration [48–50]. It was reported that Zn homeostasis plays an important role in skeletal muscle tissue since Zn ions are secondary messengers essential for the activation of a cascade of signaling pathways involved in myoblast proliferation and differentiation [50–52]. To our knowledge, there have been no previous studies investigating the inclusion of Zn-doped bioactive inorganic particles into ADA-GEL hydrogels for skeletal muscle bioprinting applications. In this study, the synthesis and characterization of Zn-doped MBGNs were carried out. The MBGNs were considered as BIFs incorporated in ADA-GEL hydrogels to form composite inks, and the effect of BIFs and Zn

ions on the swelling behavior, mechanical properties, and printability of ADA-GEL-based inks as well as the biological behavior of skeletal muscle C2C12 cells incorporated in the composite hydrogels were investigated and discussed.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), ethyl acetate (EA), tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, 99%), calcium nitrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%), zinc nitrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium (meta) periodate (NaIO_4 , BioUltra, purity $\geq 99.5\%$), gelatin (GEL, type A, 300 g Bloom, from porcine skin), calcium chloride (CaCl_2), and cell counting kit-8 (WST-8) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Ammonia (NH_3) and ethylene glycol were from VWR International. Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS), Hanks' balanced salt solution (HBSS), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, 4.5 g/l), penicillin-streptomycin (PS), and horse serum (HS) were purchased from Gibco, Thermo Fisher. Fetal bovine serum (FBS) was from Corning. Alginate (VIVAPHARM®, PH163 S2) was purchased from JRS PHARMA GmbH & Co.KG. Ethanol ($> 99.8\%$) and paraformaldehyde solution were purchased from Merck, and N-azidinitramide (HN_5O_2) was from Carl Roth. Microbial transglutaminase (mTG) was purchased from Ajinomoto Co., Inc., ACTIVA. Calcein AM, propidium iodide, rhodamine phalloidin, and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) staining dyes were purchased from Thermo Fisher. Triton® X-100 was purchased from Amresco.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Synthesis of BIFs

The MBGNs, to be used as BIFs in ADA-GEL bioinks, were synthesized employing the microemulsion-based sol-gel process reported in the literature [43,53]. MBGNs with nominal compositions of 80% SiO_2 -20% CaO (80Zn), 80% SiO_2 -18%CaO-2%ZnO (2Zn), 80% SiO_2 -15%CaO-5% ZnO (5Zn) and 80% SiO_2 -10%CaO-10%ZnO (10Zn) (mol%) were synthesized. 2.8 g of CTAB was added to 132 ml of ultrapure water and stirred at 30 °C until the white-colored solution turned transparent. The next step consisted of adding 40 ml of EA and stirring for 30 min at room temperature (RT). 28 ml of one molar ammonia solution was then added and the solution was stirred for 15 min. The precursor chemicals, including TEOS, calcium nitrate, and zinc nitrate in the case of Zn-doped MBGNs, were subsequently added into the solution in sequence, with an interval of 30 min between the components. After the inclusion of the last precursor element, the suspension was stirred for 4 h followed by centrifugation at 7830 rpm for 15 min. The sediment, which was the synthesized particles, underwent a washing process: twice with ultrapure water and once with ethanol. The particles were then dried at 60 °C overnight and calcinated at 700 °C for 3 h with a heating rate of 2 °C/min.

2.2.2. Physical and chemical analysis of the particles

2.2.2.1. Morphology. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Carl Zeiss™ AG, Auriga Zeiss) was used to characterize the morphology and surface topography of the synthesized MBGNs. The particles were loaded on SEM holders with aluminum tape, and the operated energy of the incident electrons was 1 kV.

2.2.2.2. Crystallinity. To investigate the crystallinity of MBGNs, Mini-Flex 600 diffractometer (Rigaku Co., Japan) was applied. The X-ray was induced by the equipped $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ anode ($\lambda = 0.15059$ nm) operating at 15 mA and 40 kV. MBGNs were homogeneously placed on a glass sample holder, and the diffraction patterns were recorded over an angular range (2θ) of 20–60° with a step size of 0.02° and a dwell time of 4°/min. The

crystalline or amorphous nature of MBGNs was identified by the existence of sharp peaks or broadband at a specific angular range.

2.2.2.3. Elemental composition. The chemical structure of the MBGNs and the present functional groups were investigated using attenuated total reflection Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR, Shimadzu, Japan). The absorbance spectra of the nanoparticles were recorded over a wavenumber of 400–4000 cm^{-1} with 40 scans per spectrum, a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , and the Happ-Genzel apodization.

2.2.2.4. Chemical composition. The chemical composition of the particles was measured using X-ray Fluorescence (XRF, Tiger S4 wavelength dispersive X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF) spectrometer (Bruker)). MBGNs were sieved on a 0.45 μm mesh sieve, followed by melting together with the flux (lithium tetraborate) into beads. The dilution (mixing) ratio of sample to flux in weight was 1:10 for all types of MBGNs and measured using a mask size of 34 mm under vacuum.

Chemical analysis of MBGNs was performed using inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES, Agilent 5100SVDV). Particles were converted to solution by the effect of strong acids (HCl, HNO_3 , and HF), temperature, and pressure in microwave digestion equipment (Berghof, Speedwave 4) in three replicates. Calibration of the instrument was performed by dilution of certified reference materials (Analytika Praha). Ion concentrations were measured using the emission lines of 317.933 nm (in radial view) for Ca ions and 334.502 nm (in axial view) for Zn ions. Due to the possibility of the formation of volatile SiF_4 after the addition of HF during microwave decomposition, the SiO_2 content was not reported. To deal with non-spectral interferences, the intensities of the internal standard were continuously measured.

2.2.2.5. Particle porosity. Liquid nitrogen adsorption isotherm measurement using a Micromeritics® ASAP 2460 system (Georgia, USA) was performed to determine the porosity properties of MBGNs. 200 mg of the particles were weighed and degassed under vacuum conditions at -200°C overnight. The specific surface area of particles was determined by Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface area characterization at -196°C , while Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) analysis was used to determine the cumulative pore volume and average pore diameter of the particles.

2.2.2.6. Ion release profile. Ion release profiles of MBGNs in DPBS over seven days were assessed using inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS, iCAP RQ, ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, USA). Samples were prepared by immersing 0.1% (w/v) MBGNs in DPBS, and the supernatants were collected after 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 24, 72, and 168 h. Subsequently, 0.69% HNO_3 aqueous solution was mixed with the collected supernatant samples at a volume ratio of 50:1. A Zn standard from Merck (1000 mg/l) was used to prepare a standard curve by diluting it with a nitric acid solution to yield 10, 1, 0.1, 0.01, and 0.001 mg/l standards. The respective Zn ion concentrations were calculated from the standard curve. Similar standard curves were applied to Ca ion and Si ion.

2.2.2.7. Cytotoxicity. Potential cytotoxicity of MBGNs on a mouse myoblast cell line (C2C12 cells, Leibniz Institute DSMZ), was assessed using an indirect cytotoxicity test. The cells were cultured in a growth medium, comprising high glucose DMEM supplemented with 10% (v/v) FBS and 1% PS. To extract ions from the MBGNs into the cell medium, 0.1% (w/v) of MBGNs were added to the growth medium and incubated at 37°C in a shaking incubator for 24 h. Afterward, the mixture was centrifuged at 4500 rpm for 5 min, and the supernatant was filtrated under sterile conditions with 0.22 μm sterile filters (Rotilab-syringe filters, PVDF, Carl Roth). C2C12 cells with 10^5 cells/well were seeded in a 24-well plate (Sarstedt) filled with 1 ml growth medium and incubated

at 37°C , 5% CO_2 for 24 h. After 24 h, the cell medium was replaced by 1 ml of ion-containing growth medium. A minimum of three replicates per composition were applied. To determine cell viability, 1% of water-soluble tetrazolium-salt-based WST-8 metabolic assay was performed on days 1 and 3. After an incubation time of 3 h, 100 μl of each sample ($n = 3$) was pipetted inside a 96-well plate as technical triplicates, and the absorption was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (FLUOstar Omega, BMG Labtech, Germany).

2.2.3. Synthesis of ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs inks

2.2.3.1. Synthesis of ADA. The synthesis of ADA followed the protocol from Karakaya et al. [21]. The synthesis procedure was executed under dark conditions and at RT. Initially, 10 g of alginate was combined with 50 ml of ethanol. Meanwhile, 2 g of sodium (meta) periodate was dissolved in 50 ml of ultrapure water (Milli-Q, UPW, Direct-Q, Merck Millipore, US). The sodium (meta) periodate solution was added dropwise into the alginate solution, and the solution was stirred for 6 h. Afterward, 10 ml of ethylene glycol was added to the reaction mixture to quench the excess of periodate ions, and the solution was stirred for another 30 min followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 3 min to enable decantation of the ethanol phase. The sediment was again mixed with ultrapure water and subjected to dialysis using Standard RC tubing (diameter = 32 mm, MWCO 6–8 kD, Spectra/Por1 Dialysis Membrane, Spectrum Laboratories) immersed in ultrapure water for 72 h, during which the water was changed every 24 h. The collected ADA solution was frozen at -21°C and freeze-dried to yield the final ADA product (Alpha 1–4, LSC Plus, Christ, Germany).

2.2.3.2. ADA-GEL ink preparation. To formulate pure 2.5%ADA-3.75% GEL hydrogel inks (w/v), 5% (w/v) of ADA was dissolved in DPBS and stirred at RT. Simultaneously, 7.5% (w/v) of GEL was dissolved in DPBS and stirred at 37°C . The ADA and GEL solutions were then combined at a 1:1 volume ratio and stirred for 10 min at 37°C . For the formulation of composite inks, MBGNs, used as BIFs, were added to the ADA solution. In particular, 0.1% (w/v) referred to the final volume of ADA-GEL of 8020, 2Zn, 5Zn, or 10Zn BIFs were added and stirred for 5 min at RT. To ensure proper dispersion of the particles, the solution underwent ultrasonic processing for 15 min, followed by an additional stirring step. Subsequently, the GEL solution was added into the ADA/BIF suspension at 37°C for 10 min, leading to the final hydrogel ink composition. The inks used for mass loss study, mechanical test, and cell study were prepared under sterile conditions. The BIF particles were treated at 160°C for 2 h for sterilization prior to use. ADA solution was filtered through 0.45 μm sterile filters and GEL solution was filtered through 0.22 μm filters. CaCl_2 was used as an ionic crosslinker for ADA to crosslink the hydrogel-based inks, and mTG was used as an enzymatic crosslinker for GEL chains. To prepare the crosslinker solution, 5% (w/v) of mTG powder was dissolved in 0.1 M CaCl_2 solution at RT and shielded from the light.

2.2.4. Physical and chemical analysis of the hydrogel-based inks

2.2.4.1. Swelling and mass loss studies. To investigate the swelling behavior with dimensional change of ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs hydrogels, samples ($n = 6$) were prepared using silicon molds with a diameter of 8 mm and a height of 4 mm. The inks were pipetted into the molds and crosslinked at RT for 20 min. After 20 min, the samples were washed with HBSS once and recorded by a digital camera. The samples were immersed in HBSS and incubated at 37°C , 5% CO_2 , and 95% relative humidity. After 0, 1, 3, and 7 days of incubation, the samples were recorded by a digital camera.

The mass change of the ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs hydrogels was evaluated based on their weight changes over time. The weight of samples was measured at specific time points: 0, 30, 60, 120, and 180,

and 240 min, as well as 1, 3, 7, 10, 14, and 21 days. The samples were immersed in HBSS, which was changed every 2–3 days, and incubated at 37 °C, 5% CO₂, and 95% relative humidity. The weight (*W*) of the sample at time point *t* (*W_t*) related to its initial weight at time point 0 (*W₀*) was calculated using the equation below:

$$\text{Weight change [\%]} = \frac{W_t}{W_0} \times 100$$

2.2.4.2. Mechanical (stiffness) analysis. The stiffness analysis of ADA-GEL-based hydrogels was conducted using the CellScale MicroTester (CellScale Biomaterials Testing, Waterloo, Canada). The hydrogel inks were dispensed into silicon molds measuring 5 mm in diameter and 2 mm in height. These samples were then crosslinked for 20 min at RT and subsequently incubated in DMEM for a duration of up to 14 days. Compression tests were performed on days 0, 1, 3, 7, and 14. Throughout the measurement process, the samples were immersed in a bath of HBSS maintained at 37 °C. The compression testing utilized cantilevers with a 60 mm beam length, diameters of 0.4064 (all samples on d0 and d1 as well as ADA-GEL, ADA-GEL-8020, and ADA-GEL-2Zn on d3), 0.3048 (ADA-GEL-5Zn and ADA-GEL-10Zn on d3 and all samples on d7), and 0.1524 (all samples on d14) mm, and equipped with a 6 × 6 mm² plate for applying compression to the samples. The loading and relaxation cycles were set at 30-s intervals each. Stiffness calculations (*n* = 5) were derived within a designated strain range of 1–3%.

2.2.4.3. Rheological characterization. Rheological measurements were conducted using a AR-G2 rotational rheometer (TA Instruments Ltd., USA) with a 40 mm, 2° cone-plate geometry at 25 °C. A Peltier-element was used for temperature control, and a solvent trap was applied to prevent drying of the samples. The inks were prepared as described in section 2.2.3. For each test, 1 ml of the ink was loaded onto the geometry and cooled down until the set temperature was reached. A frequency sweep in the angular frequency range of 0.1 to 100 rad/s at oscillation strain of 5% was performed (*n* = 3). The storage and loss modulus as well as the value of complex viscosity of the inks were recorded.

2.2.5. 3D printing of the hydrogel-based inks

To access the printability of the ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs inks, pre-defined structures (linear pattern with an infill density of 14.5%, Fig. S1(a)) were printed using the extrusion-based 3D printer BioX (CELLINK, Sweden). The inks were prepared following previously described procedures and loaded into 3 ml cartridges, which were connected to 27 Gauge conical nozzles (CELLINK, Sweden) and positioned at the print head with a preset temperature of 25 °C. A consistent printing speed of 5 mm/s was employed across all structures, with 100 ms pre- and post-flow settings. To ensure continuous and uniform filament extrusion, the printing pressure was adjusted according to the specific characteristics of the inks. The pore area of the printed constructs was quantified and compared to the ideal pore area given by the computer-aided design (CAD) model. The thickness of the printed structures was also measured as an indicator for proper layer-by-layer filament deposition. Three structures (*n* = 3) were printed for each composition at two time points: 15 and 55 min, which was defined as the duration for which the ink had been used for printing at 25 °C after being freshly prepared.

As an additional characterization of the printability of the inks, the filament fusion test (FFT) and filament collapse test (FCT) were carried out [54]. The resolution tree shown in Fig. S1(b) composed of parallel strands with decreasing spacing was printed with three replicates for each combination at 15 and 55 min. The distances between two subsequent filaments in the meandering pattern were 2, 1.5, 1, 0.75, and 0.5 mm, and the resolution averaged from three prints was defined as the spacing between two adjacent lines where the inks do not flow and fuse together. In order to study the sagging and collapse behavior of an extruded filament, a single ink filament was deposited on a stand with

pillars spaced at distances of 16, 8, 4, 2, and 1 mm. The filaments were deposited three times (*n* = 3) for each ink in between time points of 15 and 55 min.

2.2.5.1. Bioprinting and cell studies. Bioprinting was conducted for ADA-GEL, ADA-GEL-8020, ADA-GEL-2Zn, ADA-GEL-5Zn, and ADA-GEL-10Zn inks incorporating C2C12 cells. The sterile inks were mixed with 2 million/ml cells gently and 3D bioprinted, similar to the method mentioned above, using the BioX 3D printer, at 25 °C, with a printing speed of 5 mm/s and 100 ms pre- and post-flow. The printed structure was a grid pattern with a dimension of 15 × 15 × 1 mm³, as shown in Fig. S1(c). Post-printing, the bioprinted structures were crosslinked, washed with HBSS, and incubated in DMEM supplemented with 1% (v/v) PS and 2% (v/v) HS, for 7 days. Cell viability within the bioprinted constructs was assessed on days 1, 3, and 7 by applying 1% (v/v) WST-8 solution. After a 3-h incubation, the absorbance of the WST-8 solution was measured at the wavelength of 450 nm. Furthermore, on day 7, staining procedures involving Live/Dead and rhodamine phalloidin/DAPI were performed. For the Live/Dead assay, a master stock solution of 4 μl/ml of Calcein AM and 4 μl/ml of propidium iodide in HBSS was applied to the bioprinted structures in the absence of light for 45 min at 37 °C. For the cytoskeleton staining, the samples were fixed using 3.75% (v/v) paraformaldehyde solution, followed by the permeabilization step using 1% Triton® X-100. Afterwards, a master stock solution of 8 μl/ml rhodamine phalloidin in HBSS was employed on the bioprinted structures at RT for an hour before the introduction of the master stock solution of 4 μl/ml DAPI in HBSS for 15 min at RT. Washing with HBSS was carried out between each staining step. The bioprinted structures were imaged using an inverted epifluorescence microscope (Axio Scope A.1, Carl Zeiss, Germany) to visualize the cellular distribution and morphology within the constructs.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. MBGNs as bioactive inorganic fillers (BIFs)

The MBGNs used in this study were designed with nominal compositions: 80% SiO₂-X% CaO-Y% ZnO (X = 20, 18, 15, or 10; Y = 0, 2, 5, or 10; mol%). Ca²⁺ has been known to be the most crucial ion for regulating muscular functions, namely contraction and relaxation of muscles, and the development of skeletal muscle cells [55–57], while Si ion has been reported to have stimulatory and protective effect on the development of C2C12 cells [58,59]. The implementation of ion-releasing MBGNs containing Ca, Si and other therapeutic ions as an ionic medicine strategy is an increasing investigated topic, and the impact of metallic ions on skeletal muscle regeneration was recently reviewed [60,61]. In this work, we focus on Zn ions which are released as part of the ionic dissolution products of Zn containing MBGNs.

The morphology and size of the MBGNs designed to be used as BIFs were analyzed from SEM images. As shown in Fig. 1, regardless of the amount of doped Zn, all types of MBGNs exhibited spherical shape and a homogenous size and shape distribution. The average diameter of the nanoparticles was measured to be 184 ± 20 nm for 8020, 144 ± 8 nm for 2Zn, 117 ± 20 nm for 5Zn, and 110 ± 10 nm for 10Zn. With an increase in the amount of Zn, the average size of the nanoparticles decreased. Neščáková et al. reported a similar size of their Zn-doped bioactive glass nanoparticles with an average particle size of 130 ± 10 nm as well as homogeneous dispersity and spherical shape [62].

The amorphous nature of the 8020 and Zn-containing MBGNs was revealed by X-ray diffraction analyses, as shown in Fig. 2(a). All MBGNs displayed similar XRD spectra with a broad band in the 2θ range of 20°–35°, ascribed to an amorphous silicate phase [63]. The absence of sharp diffraction peaks indicated the successful synthesis of Zn-containing MBGNs without the formation of crystalline phases. The FTIR spectra of MBGNs are shown in Fig. 2 (b). The characteristic

Fig. 1. Scanning electron microscopic images of synthesized (a) 8020, (b) 2Zn, (c) 5Zn, and (d) 10Zn BIFs and (e) their average diameter. (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

absorption bands of the asymmetric stretching vibration of the Si-O-Si bonding were detected at 1043 cm^{-1} as well as at the shoulders near 1215 cm^{-1} [64,65]. At 447 cm^{-1} , the intensive Si-O-Si bending vibrations of the amorphous silica network could be identified, while the peak at 798 cm^{-1} corresponds to the tetrahedral symmetric vibration of Si-O bonds in SiO_4^{4-} [66,67]. With the absence of newly formed or shifted peaks, the FTIR spectrum of 2Zn demonstrated no change in the molecular structure of the MBGNs after adding a small amount of Zn. As the concentration of Zn increased, a shoulder at around 933 cm^{-1} appeared in 5Zn and further intensified in 10Zn, which is associated with the Si-O-Zn bonds [68]. Zinc is known to act as both a network modifier and an intermediate oxide in silicate phases. As a network modifier, Zn plays the same role as Ca and interacts with the silicate network via non-bridging oxygens. When more Zn is present in the system, as assumed to be $>5\%$, Zn acts as an intermediate oxide that forms covalent linkages with the silicate network system [63,69]. The presence of an absorbance band at 933 cm^{-1} in the FTIR spectra of 5Zn and 10Zn BIFs showed that Zn was in a high enough concentration that Si-O-Zn bonds formed in the system.

The chemical composition of MBGNs detected by ICP-OES and XRF is summarized in Table 1. ICP-OES data for SiO_2 were not reported because of the possible formation of volatile SiF_4 during the decomposition process. There are no significant differences between the results of ICP-OES and XRF measurements. Compared to its nominal composition, the 8020, 2Zn, and 5Zn MBGNs had higher Si and Zn content with much lower Ca concentration, while 10Zn had higher Zn and lower Si and Ca content. The deviation of compositions was likely due to the intensive washing steps to remove excess surfactants and residues in the microemulsion-assisted sol-gel method to synthesize highly dispersed MBGNs [43]. Various factors, such as the adsorption ability of the ions,

the environment of the synthesis, pH, temperature and post-treatment could influence the final concentration of elements in the nanoparticles [43,70,71]. The deviation between nominal and actual compositions and the difficulty of predicting the final compositions have been a commonly known challenge of this method. In 8020, 2Zn, and 5Zn MBGNs, both Ca and Zn are network modifiers. However, Zn tends to be a stronger network modifier than Ca due to its higher field strength, and those loosely adsorbed to the silicate network could be washed away [43,72–75]. Consequently, the Ca concentration was much lower than its initially calculated value while a higher percentage of Si was present. On the contrary, 10Zn had lower Si content than its nominal composition, which could be due to the high amount of Zn in this composition that allows ZnO to act as an intermediate oxide [69,73]. The incorporation of Zn into the network was also confirmed by the Si-O-Zn band in the FTIR spectrum.

Liquid nitrogen adsorption isotherm measurements were performed to determine the porous structure of MBGNs. The adsorption-desorption curves (Fig. 2(c)) displayed type IV isotherms, corresponding to the category of mesoporous materials [76]. In comparison to undoped 8020, a small amount of Zn, i.e. 2Zn composition, led to an elevation in BET surface area and BJH adsorption cumulative pore volume (Table S1). As the Zn concentration further increased to 5Zn and 10Zn, the specific surface area decreased, which could be associated with the interaction of metallic ion precursors, mainly nitrate salts, with the cationic surfactant during the synthesis that caused a partial collapse of pores or pore-blocking [43]. The same trend was reported by Courtheoux et al. [77] showing that the surface area of bioactive glasses doped with Zn increased at low Zn concentrations and decreased upon further augmentation of the doping levels. Regarding average pore diameter, all MBGNs in this study have an average pore diameter of around 2 nm,

Fig. 2. Phase analysis and chemical characteristics of BIF particles using (a) XRD, (b) FTIR and (c) liquid nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm (BET analysis). (d, e) The ion release profile of BIFs in DPBS over 7 days; (f) metabolic activity of C2C12 cells measured by WST-8 analysis technique after 3 days of incubation in cell culture media containing BIFs-extracts (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

with a clear decrease in pore diameter with an increased amount of Zn, from 8020 to 10Zn (Table S1). A similar trend has been reported by Anand et al. [78] indicating that the pore volume and pore size of Zn-containing samples decreased with increasing content of Zn.

The release behavior of Si, Ca, and Zn ions from the MBGNs after incubation in PBS was measured using the ICP-MS technique, and results are displayed in Fig. 2(d,e). The cumulative Si release curves show that there was no burst release of Si into PBS at 37 °C in the first 3 h, and the

release of Si ions was steady over 7 days for all MBGNs. Compared to 2Zn and 5Zn with resembling amounts of Si ions, 8020 exhibited a faster Si release profile from day 1 to day 3. Consistent with the findings from other research groups [62,63,79], the addition of Zn delayed the leaching of Si and Ca ions out from MBGNs. Based on ICP-OES and XRF analyses, 2Zn and 5Zn MBGNs contained the same amounts of Ca. However, a higher concentration of Ca was released within 7 days from 2Zn compared to 5Zn. Additionally, while the final Ca release from 8020

Table 1
Chemical compositions of the synthesized BIFs determined by XRF and ICP-OES.

	XRF (wt%)			ICP-OES (wt%)		
	CaO	ZnO	SiO ₂	CaO	ZnO	SiO ₂
80SiO ₂ -20CaO	6.4 ± 0.1	–	82.5 ± 0.5	6.4 ± 0.3	–	Not reported: formation of volatile SiF ₄ during decomposition process
80SiO ₂ -18CaO- 2ZnO	4.6 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.1	86 ± 0.4	4.8 ± 0.1	3.2 ± 0.1	
80SiO ₂ -15CaO- 5ZnO	4 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.1	83.2 ± 0.5	4.2 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.3	
80SiO ₂ -10CaO- 10ZnO	1.8 ± 0.1	24.8 ± 0.8	69.8 ± 0.5	1.7 ± 0.2	25 ± 1.0	

and 2Zn over 7 days was similar, the leaching rate of Ca from 2Zn was slower, especially in the first 24 h. It is reported that Zn as a dopant for calcium-silicate-based nanoparticles can stabilize the network system and therefore it can delay the dissolution and release of e.g. Ca ions [62,77,79]. This phenomenon is observed in the MBGNs developed in this study and confirms the role of ZnO as a network former that not only reduces the number of non-bridging oxygens but also carries excess negative charges which were balanced by Ca ions, thus restraining the release of Ca ions [63,73]. The opposite behavior is observed in 10Zn MBGNs, where an evident increase in the release of Si and Zn was detected from day 3 to day 7, indicating the breakdown of the glass network.

Cytotoxicity of MBGNs to C2C12 myoblasts was tested indirectly by exposing the C2C12 cells to the extracts collected from 0.1 wt% MBGNs incubated in the culture medium for 24 h. Cells were incubated for up to 3 days with a cell culture medium containing extracts, and their viability was measured after 24 and 72 h of exposure (Fig. 2(f)). After 24 h of incubation, cells treated with 8020 and 2Zn extracts demonstrated higher viability (103% and 113%, respectively) in comparison to the control (100% for cells treated with cell culture medium without extracts) while cells in the 5Zn and 10Zn environment showed lower viability (89% and 91%, respectively). It must be noted that there were significant differences between 2Zn and 5Zn ($*** p < 0.001$), 2Zn and 10Zn ($*** p < 0.001$), and 8020 and 5Zn ($*p < 0.1$). The cells exposed to 2Zn-extracts exhibited the highest cell viability after 24 and 72 h, with a statistically significant difference compared to the control, 8020, 5Zn, and 10Zn ($*** p < 0.001$) after 72 h. Despite the minor difference, all types of MBGNs led to higher cell viability than 80%, conveying the idea that the extracts of 0.1 wt% of 8020, 2Zn, 5Zn, and 10Zn were nontoxic to C2C12 cells.

3.2. ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIF inks

3.2.1. Swelling and mass loss studies

A significant advantage of hydrogels is their high water content and their swelling capacity that absorb and retain large amounts of water [23]. This characteristic makes hydrogels similar to natural living tissues [15,17]. The dimensional change of pure ADA-GEL hydrogel as well as various composites: ADA-GEL-8020, ADA-GEL-2Zn, ADA-GEL-5Zn, and ADA-GEL-10Zn was measured after incubation in HBSS solution for 0, 1, 3, and 7 days. Fig. S2 shows that, from visual observation, the increase in diameter of ADA-GEL-5Zn and ADA-GEL-10Zn was higher than that of ADA-GEL, ADA-GEL-8020, and ADA-GEL-2Zn, with the pure ADA-GEL samples displaying the smallest deviation from their initial size.

The free volume within the hydrogel matrix is the base for hydrogel swelling, which takes place until the osmotic pressure caused by absorbing the surrounding solution and the elasticity of the polymeric network reaches an equilibrium [80]. Incorporating nanoparticles adds

free volume to the hydrogel matrix by disrupting the ideal polymer chain alignment or entanglement, leading to a looser arrangement of polymer chains and therefore higher solution uptake into the matrix.

Biodegradation is advantageous for scaffolds because after transplantation, the scaffold can be substituted by newly formed tissue. The weight loss of pure ADA-GEL hydrogel and composite ADA-GEL-8020, ADA-GEL-2Zn, ADA-GEL-5Zn, and ADA-GEL-10Zn hydrogels was recorded over 21 days of incubation in DMEM medium. The time-dependent weight changes can be divided into two stages. In the first stage, the hydrogel samples swelled and gained weight due to the intake of the medium. Regardless of the compositions, the weight of all samples greatly increased after 1 day of incubation and reached a maximal value on day 3, which corresponded to the trend of change in the diameter of the samples. Their average weight gain demonstrated no statistically significant difference between pure and composite hydrogels. The second stage, which continued until day 21 of incubation, was the reduction in weight due to the release of uncrosslinked polymer segments and particles and the dissociation of the whole structure.

As shown in Fig. 3(a), according to the average weight values, Zn-doped BIF-containing samples were observed to have larger change in weight than other ADA-GEL hydrogels. An explanation could be that the incorporation of Zn ions leads to an inhomogeneous crosslinking of ADA chains because the affinity of alginate/ADA to react with Zn²⁺ is lower than that with Ca²⁺ [81,82]. The crosslinking of ADA with calcium ions results in an egg-box formation of polymer chains based on the bidentate binding mode between calcium ions and two carboxylate groups of ADA [83]. Zn²⁺-crosslinked polymer chains exhibit an analogous egg-box formation, which, however, involves only one carboxylate group of ADA [84]. The monodentate binding between Zn²⁺ and ADA gives rise to a more flexible arrangement and movement of the polymer chains. Additionally, the difference in the ionic radii of Zn²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ions was also reported to be a cause for the different hydrogel behavior. Falcone et al. [85] demonstrated that Zn²⁺, with its smaller ionic radius than Ca²⁺, attracts more water molecules. The increased hydration leads to a greater distance between Zn nuclei and the carboxylate groups of ADA, which reduces Coulombic attraction and consequently weakens the structure [85]. In the next section of our study, it is also shown that the Zn-doped BIF-containing samples show lower mechanical properties, which can be related to the fact of having a more flexible molecular arrangement.

Since Ca²⁺ has a higher affinity to the carboxylate group than Zn²⁺, calcium ions were expected to replace the monodentate-bound Zn ions during the external crosslinking step with CaCl₂ solution that offered an excessive amount of Ca²⁺ [81,82]. However, Gibb's free energy for Zn²⁺-induced bonds is higher (~ 42 kJ/mol) [86] than that of Ca²⁺-induced bonds (~ 28 kJ/mol) [87], allowing the formed monodentate bonds to be more stable and difficult to break and replace. The presence of Zn²⁺ complicated the re-arrangement and re-crosslinking of ADA chains with Ca²⁺ ions, and the monodentate binding mode led to a looser polymeric network and easier shape change, thereby making Zn-containing samples prone to more significant dimensional changes and possibly faster hydrolysis. Although Zn-doped BIF-containing samples exhibited larger dimensional change in diameter and a faster trend of weight loss by average weight, the results of weight change over the 21-day incubation period did not clearly display statistically significant differences.

3.2.2. Mechanical analysis

It is crucial for a scaffold to mimic the mechanochemical microenvironment of the targeted natural tissue, which supports better cell interaction and tissue development during the regeneration process [2,88]. Stiffness plays an important role in the mechanocompatibility of a scaffold [89]. The stiffness of pure ADA-GEL hydrogel and composite ADA-GEL-8020, ADA-GEL-2Zn, ADA-GEL-5Zn, and ADA-GEL-10Zn hydrogels was investigated by applying compression tests to the samples after incubation in DMEM medium at 37 °C for different time points (0, 1, 3, 7, and 14 days). In consideration of the intrinsic properties of

Fig. 3. (a) Mass loss behavior of the hydrogel samples incubated in DMEM over 21 days ($n = 6$); (b) effective modulus of the samples incubated in DMEM over 14 days ($n = 5$); (c) storage and (d) loss modulus of the hydrogel inks measured with frequency sweep ($n = 3$); (e) shift from viscous-dominated to elastic-dominated behavior of the inks with increasing angular frequency; (f) value of complex viscosity of the inks from frequency sweep (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

hydrogel samples that deformed multi-dimensionally during the compression testing, the term “effective modulus” was used (Fig. 3(b)). The effective modulus of each composition at each time point was calculated and plotted after applying the loading and relaxation cycles set at 30-s intervals and a designated strain range of 1–3%. The average effective modulus of as-prepared samples of all compositions was higher than 1 kPa on day 0, with ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-8020 groups reaching almost 2 kPa. After 1 day of incubation, ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-8020 exhibited similar modulus values on day 0; however, the effective modulus of Zn-incorporated samples decreased sharply, with ADA-GEL-10Zn decreasing the most to 0.5 kPa. Significant reduction of modulus

for all samples took place from day 1 to 3, which was the time point when the samples were fully swollen according to the swelling and degradation tests. As expected from the previous analysis, the weaker crosslinked network of composite hydrogels with Zn-doped fillers resulted in a lower stiffness of the materials. From day 3 to day 14, the effective modulus of all samples gradually decreased, while samples with higher Zn doping always displayed lower average stiffness. This behavior can be explained by the variation of Gibbs free energy and binding mode of zinc ions to the polymer network, which allows for greater water uptake in Zn-containing samples and a less dense arrangement of the polymer chains. After 14 days of incubation in

DMEM, the samples were not completely dissolved but became challenging to handle due to the high mass loss and lost shape integrity. Therefore, the mechanical investigation was carried out until day 14 of incubation. Compared to the recent study by Bider et al. [90], where the same concentration and ratio of ADA-GEL and the same measurement device were applied, our hydrogels exhibited lower effective moduli. This could be attributed to the differences in the oxidation degree of ADA, with theirs being 13% and ours 19%, as well as the strain range used to calculate the modulus, which was up to 10% in their study and 1–3% in ours.

3.2.3. Rheological characterization

Rheological measurements were conducted to evaluate the printability of the hydrogels. The oscillation strain of 5% was selected by amplitude sweep, which defined the viscoelastic region of the inks. Fig. 3(c) and (d) show the storage (G') and loss (G'') moduli of the ADA-GEL and composite inks over an angular frequency range of 0.1 to 100 rad/s. Fig. 3(e) shows an example of plotting both G' and G'' of the same ink in one graph. At lower angular frequencies, the inks exhibited predominantly elastic behavior, displayed by $G' > G''$. As the angular frequency increased, the storage and loss moduli intersected, marking a transition to viscous dominance. The value of complex viscosity of the inks exhibited a decreasing trend with increasing angular frequency (Fig. 3(f)), namely a shear-thinning behavior. This property is desirable for 3D printing applications, further supporting the suitability of the developed hydrogels as inks in this process. Likewise the viscoelastic behavior of alginate-based inks has been also reported in the literature

[23,91–93].

Despite slight variations in measured values potentially attributed to fluctuations in ambient temperature and humidity, and differences in composite ink preparation compared to pure ADA-GEL due to prolonged mixing and ultrasonication to disperse nanoparticles, comparable rheological properties among the five ink compositions were observed.

3.3. Printability of the ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs inks

The ADA-GEL-based inks used in this study are temperature-responsive due to the presence of gelatin. The thermally responsive characteristics of gelatin make this biopolymer highly utilized in the field of 3D printing. However, at the same time, the working temperature is decisive for the properties of inks, the printing processes, and the quality of the printed structures [94,95]. Additionally, the behavior of ADA-GEL inks is time-dependent, which is influenced by temperature changes, Schiff's base formation, and in-situ ion-induced crosslinking over time [20,65]. For example, the strands printed with ADA-GEL inks 15 min after preparation of the gel (Fig. 4(e)) were smoother while the printability after 55 min was reduced and the printed strands had an irregular shape due to the physical gelation of the gelatin in the ink over time (Fig. 4(f)). Therefore, in order to better understand the printability of the inks, an analysis of pore area, thickness of the printed structures, filament fusion, and filament collapse behavior resembling printing accuracy was carried out.

Fig. 4. (a) Top view and (b) side view of a printed ADA-GEL structure, crosslinked with 0.1 M CaCl₂ for 10 min; (c) top view and (b) side view of a printed ADA-GEL-10Zn structure, crosslinked with 0.1 M CaCl₂ for 10 min (a-d: scale bar = 2 mm); (e) strands from a ADA-GEL-10Zn structure printed at $t = 15$ min; (f) strands from a ADA-GEL-10Zn structure printed at $t = 55$ min (e, f: scale bar = 0.5 mm); (g,h) one layer of printed meandering lines to check the distribution of BIF particles (g,h: scale bar = 1 mm); (i) average pore area of printed structures (red dash line: ideal pore area calculated from the CAD model); (j) average thickness of the printed structures (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

3.3.1. Pore area

A 3D model of the selected structure as shown in Fig. S1(a) consists of two different kinds of pores. The large hexagonal pore was calculated to have an ideal pore area of 9.3 mm^2 , while the small triangular pore had an ideal area of 0.9 mm^2 . In all cases, the small triangular pores were not recognizable which can be attributed to the intrinsic characteristics of the hydrogels that the printed strands tend to spread and fuse. Likewise, instead of an ideal hexagonal shape, the large pores lost sharp angles and became circular. Nevertheless, both pure ADA-GEL and composite inks exhibited good printability, as demonstrated by the continuously extruded inks, which formed smooth filaments and were deposited layer-by-layer without collapsing. The printed structures were intact and the height was able to reach $>3 \text{ mm}$ with only a slight distortion of the structure (Fig. 4(a-d) and Fig. S3). In composite inks, the homogeneous distribution of nanoparticles within the hydrogel can be clearly identified in Fig. 4(g,h). The presence of 0.1% (w/v) BIFs seemed to barely affect the printability of ADA-GEL inks, which was consistent with the results of the rheological characterization. This behavior could be associated with the low amount and homogeneous distribution of the nanoparticles in the system. Additionally, the pore area of all compositions of inks at printing time points of 15 and 55 min was also similar, as shown in Fig. 4(i). The average pore area of ADA-GEL printed at $t = 15 \text{ min}$ was 7.4 mm^2 and at $t = 55 \text{ min}$ was 7.5 mm^2 . Similarly, the pore area for composite inks was 7.2 and 7.3 mm^2 for ADA-GEL-8020, 7.9 and 8.0 mm^2 for ADA-GEL-2Zn, 7.9 and 8.1 mm^2 for ADA-GEL-5Zn, and 7.9 and 7.7 mm^2 for ADA-GEL-10Zn, printed at $t = 15$ and 55 min , respectively. However, it was notable that the printing pressure required to extrude smooth filaments at 55 min was greater than that at 15 min. For instance, the pressure needed for printing ADA-GEL at $t = 15 \text{ min}$

was 35 kPa , while 60 kPa pressure was necessary for printing the same ink at $t = 55 \text{ min}$. The printing pressure related to the printing time could be due to the gelation state of the inks altered over time (Fig. S4) [96].

3.3.2. Structure thickness accuracy

The predetermined model specified a theoretical thickness of 3 mm for the printed structures. In practical cases, the average thickness of the printed structures exceeded the ideal thickness, reaching 3.6 mm for ADA-GEL, 3.2 mm for ADA-GEL-8020, 3.5 mm for ADA-GEL-2Zn, 3.9 mm for ADA-GEL-5Zn, and 3.7 mm for ADA-GEL-10Zn composite ink (Fig. 4(j)). One possible reason could be the difference in the strand's diameter and adjustment of printing parameters, particularly printing pressure, employed during the printing process. As the printing pressure was adapted, often significantly increased to ensure consistent extrusion and deposition of inks, the deposited filaments might have surpassed the ideal nozzle size, with the deposited ink volume compensating for gravitational-induced filament sagging.

3.3.3. Filament fusion test (FFT) and Filament collapse test (FCT)

Fusion of filaments in a printed pattern could result in an increase in the width of strands and a decrease in the pore sizes. In order to determine how closely two adjacent filaments can be deposited without fusing together as an indication of the resolution of the ink, the filament fusion test (FFT) [54] was conducted. A meandering pattern with decreasing distances between two subsequent filaments was printed, and the results are shown in Fig. 5(a). The smallest distance at which two filaments could be independently identified without fusing was recorded as proof of the resolution of the structure for each ink. Fig. 5(b)

Fig. 5. Filament fusion test (FFT): (a) digital images of resolution trees printed using different inks at time points of 15 and 55 min (scale bars = 10 mm), (b) minimal distance between two non-fused filaments (resolution of filaments).

displays the average resolution calculated from three replicates at each printing time point, namely 15 and 55 min, showing no significant difference in the resolution among all the ADA-GEL-based inks developed in this study. All inks were able to print filaments with identifiable distances of 0.75 to 1 mm without fusion.

During printing, the sagging or collapse of the deposited filaments often occurs since ADA-GEL-based hydrogels are mechanically soft [54,90]. To reveal the sagging or collapse behavior of an ink, a filament collapse test [54] was performed. The deformation of suspended filaments was initiated by gravity and related to the weight of the suspended material. As the gap distance between the two pillars increased, more inks contributed to the deformation of the filament, and therefore, the deflection of the filaments became larger. By carefully adjusting the printing pressures, both pure ADA-GEL and composite inks were able to form continuous filaments on pillars at all distances, as shown in Fig. S5. The results thus demonstrated the suitability of all developed inks for 3D printing.

3.4. Bioprinting of muscle cells and ADA-GEL-based inks

In this study, the developed ADA-GEL-based composite hydrogels were evaluated for 3D bioprinting of skeletal muscle C2C12 cells. The myoblasts were thereby incorporated with ADA-GEL, ADA-GEL-8020, ADA-GEL-2Zn, ADA-GEL-5Zn, and ADA-GEL-10Zn hydrogels, resulting

in five different bioinks for the bioprinting process. Many factors within the bioprinting process and the resulting constructs greatly impact the viability and functionality of cells encapsulated in hydrogels. Factors such as the applied printing pressure and the size/shape of the nozzle influence the exertion of shear stress on the cells, potentially causing harmful effects if excessively high [97]. In addition, the porosity of the printed structures determines the transportation of nutrients, oxygen, and waste products [98]. Therefore, bioprinting was conducted to validate the suitability of the ADA-GEL-based bioinks for biofabrication applications of muscle cells. The mitochondrial activity assay WST-8 was performed on the bioprinted structures after 1, 3, and 7 days of incubation to measure the metabolic activity and proliferation of metabolically active cells. The results are displayed in Fig. 6. After 1 and 3 days of incubation, the average absorbance values for cells encapsulated in composites were higher than those in pure ADA-GEL, demonstrating that the incorporation of calcium-silicate-based BIFs led to a supportive effect on the activity of C2C12 cells in ADA-GEL based inks. Following a 7-day culture, an increase in cell number across all five inks is evident, suggesting that both pure ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs composite inks exhibited cytocompatibility. After 7 days of culture, composite hydrogels containing Zn-doped BIFs showed significantly higher absorbance values, reaching 0.35 ± 0.02 for ADA-GEL-5Zn, compared to pure ADA-GEL having an absorbance of 0.31 ± 0.01 . Heid et al. [65] reported comparable findings showing that the inclusion

Fig. 6. Fluorescent microscopic images of bioprinted cells stained with Live/Dead assay after 7 days of incubation within (a) ADA-GEL, (b) ADA-GEL-8020, (c) ADA-GEL-2Zn, (d) ADA-GEL-5Zn, (e) ADA-GEL-10Zn; (f) proliferation of bioprinted cells measured by WST-8 assay over 7 days. Green: calcein, red: propidium iodide (* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

of 0.1% calcium-silicate bioactive glass particles as BIFs in ADA-GEL hydrogels led to higher NIH/3T3 mouse fibroblast cell viability, and both pure and composite hydrogels exhibited good cytocompatibility.

Fluorescent staining was further carried out to visualize cell distribution and morphology. Live/Dead images (Fig. 6) showed that the cells

were evenly distributed in the hydrogel matrix, and no strong differences in cell distribution between ADA-GEL and ADA-GEL-BIFs were visible. However, a noticeable number of cells was visible outside the printed strands, indicating that the current ADA-GEL formulation could be further optimized for C2C12 cells. Nevertheless, it was expected that

Fig. 7. Fluorescent microscopic images of bioprinted cells with cytoskeleton and nuclei staining after 7 days of incubation within ADA-GEL, ADA-GEL-8020, ADA-GEL-2Zn, ADA-GEL-5Zn, and ADA-GEL-10Zn. Red: rhodamine phalloidin, blue: DAPI.

cells tended to migrate toward the edges of the filaments, as nutrients and oxygen were supplied through the external cell medium. In addition to Live/Dead assay, rhodamine-phalloidin and DAPI stainings were performed on the C2C12 cell-laden constructs to assess the morphology of bioprinted cells within the filaments after 7 days of culture. It is clearly seen that cells in the filaments were elongated and connected to each other in all five inks. Although the difference is minor, Fig. 7 shows that cells in pure ADA-GEL hydrogel were less elongated along the printing direction in comparison to those in e.g. ADA-GEL-8020 and ADA-GEL-2Zn, which demonstrated highly elongated and oriented cells. Distler et al. [99] have previously explored the possibility to orient myoblasts through the extrusion printing process and discussed the orientation of macromolecules and cells in bioinks following the extrusion direction, further stabilizing the oriented bioink using external crosslinker such as divalent ions. The hypothesis was that the cells grew along the oriented and crosslinked polymer chains having cell adhesion motifs, leading to cell elongation along the printing direction over time [99].

The development of composite hydrogels for 3D bioprinting skeletal muscle cells, aimed at enhancing cell behavior and alignment, has become a prominent topic in recent years. For example, Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. [100] investigated gelatin methacryloyl (GelMA)-based bioinks containing MBGNs and C2C12 cells, which were used to bioprint (with or without MBGNs) using a light-based bioprinting system. After 15 days of incubation, cell viability, metabolic activity, and alignment in the composite group were significantly higher than in the GelMA control, likely due to ion release from the MBGNs. It was reported that cell alignment was inhomogeneous throughout the bioprinted construct and cells located at the edges and inner regions did not consistently orient in the same direction. In spite of that, the presence of MBGNs resulted in an enhancement of cell alignment within the hydrogel [100]. In a related study, Ceballos-González et al. [101] designed multi-layered composite GelMA/alginate hydrogels where C2C12 cells were not in direct contact with calcium silicate bioactive glass, however cells were influenced by the released ions from the Ca silicate fillers. Although increased cytotoxicity was observed at higher concentrations of fillers, the alignment of cells, the metabolic activity, and the number of nuclei per cell were enhanced [101].

According to the printability analysis and bioprinting results of our study, ADA-GEL-based bioinks incorporating MBGNs as BIFs demonstrated favorable bioprintability, considering both manufacturing and biological perspectives. The addition of BIFs is confirmed to be advantageous for myoblast development [60,100–102]. The unresolved question in this study is the difficulty of discerning the distinct effects of either calcium ions or Zn ions individually. Westhauser et al. [103] reported that low concentrations of Zn-doped MBGNs had a similar influence on cell viability as undoped particles. The concentration of BIFs (1 mg/ml) in the current system was notably lower in comparison to the cell count (2 million/ml). The presence of dopant ions such as Zn in the system was thus extremely reduced, resulting in an indistinguishable effect of a specific ion type on cell behavior. In spite of that, the developed ADA-GEL composite bioinks integrating mesoporous bioactive inorganic fillers provide a valuable platform for advancing research on bioinks for skeletal muscle regeneration through biofabrication techniques, and they offer the potential to further investigate the effect of biologically active ions on muscle cell behavior in 3D.

4. Conclusions

This study investigated the impact of Zn doped MBGNs as BIFs on various properties of ADA-GEL composite hydrogels, including swelling behavior, degradation rate, mechanical strength, and 3D bioprinting of composite inks with C2C12 cells. MBGNs doped with 2, 5, and 10% of Zn ions were amorphous and showed spherical shape. The incorporation of Zn retarded the leaching of Si and Ca ions from MBGNs, which could be a benefit in regard to the controlled release of ions. The indirect cell

culture test revealed the cytocompatibility of the used MBGNs. ADA-GEL-based composite hydrogel inks were successfully prepared with excellent printability and stability after the crosslinking process. It was found that the substitution of Ca by Zn caused the hydrogels to swell to a greater degree and deform more considerably after immersion in aqueous solutions. This behavior was explained due to the higher polymer chain arrangement caused by the monodentate Zn-ADA binding with high Gibb's free energy. The bioprinting of C2C12 cells revealed high proliferation of cells over 7 days of culture in the presence of 0.1% Zn-BIFs composite ADA-GEL, supporting the potential of the composite for skeletal muscle tissue engineering applications. Additionally, the cells within the bioprinted filaments elongated in the direction of printing, which further serves as a basis for the development of myoblasts. Although the mechanical properties of hydrogels still require optimization for skeletal muscle tissue applications, this study demonstrates the promising role of Zn-containing BIFs in enhancing the 3D printing properties of ADA-GEL-based hydrogels and cell proliferation, laying the groundwork for future investigations of ion loaded bioinks for muscle tissue engineering.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hsuan-Heng Lu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Clara Froidevaux:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Isabell Biermann:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Hana Kaňková:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Margitta Büchner:** Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Dirk W. Schubert:** Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Sahar Salehi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Aldo R. Boccaccini:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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